

Fabrication and Characterization of Silver-Based Thin-Film Temperature Sensors Using Image Reversal Lithography for Educational Purposes

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Abstract

This work demonstrates the complete fabrication cycle of a silver-based microtechnological temperature sensor in an academic cleanroom environment. The fabrication process comprises wafer dicing, resist coating via spin-coating, UV lithography with image reversal process, metallization by DC magnetron sputtering, photoresist lift-off, and electrical as well as thermal characterization. The fabricated sensor structures were investigated with respect to film thickness, edge quality, electrical resistance, and temperature coefficient. The measured temperature coefficient of $\alpha = (3.0 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ shows good agreement with literature values for sputtered silver films and is expectedly lower than the value for bulk silver due to thin-film effects. The process yield of 20% provides a realistic benchmark for student laboratory courses and identifies critical process steps for future optimization, particularly particle control, development time, and lift-off procedure.

Keywords: Temperature sensor, RTD, thin-film technology, image reversal lithography, DC magnetron sputtering, lift-off process, silver, microsystems technology

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Background

Microfabrication technologies form the foundation of modern sensing, actuation, and integrated microsystems (MEMS). Resistance-based temperature sensors, also known as Resistance Temperature Detectors (RTDs), are among

the most widely used temperature sensors in industrial measurement technology [1]. They are characterized by high accuracy, long-term stability, and an almost linear relationship between resistance and temperature.

While platinum is the standard material for commercial RTDs due to its chemical stability (e.g., Pt100, Pt1000), silver offers a higher temperature coefficient and thus greater sensitivity as an alternative material [2]. However, silver is more susceptible to oxidation and mechanical damage, which imposes special requirements on the fabrication process.

1.2 Objectives

In this work, a complete microstructuring process for the fabrication of thin-film, silver-based temperature sensors was carried out. The objectives were:

1. Practical execution of a multi-step lithographic process under clean-room conditions,
2. Characterization of the fabricated structures with respect to geometrical and electrical properties,
3. Quantification of the temperature coefficient and comparison with literature values,
4. Identification of typical process errors and derivation of optimization strategies.

This work documents the entire process chain in detail and critically evaluates the achieved results in the context of established microfabrication techniques.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Operating Principle of Resistance-Based Temperature Sensors

The electrical resistance of metallic conductors is temperature-dependent and can be described to first approximation by the linear relationship

$$R(T) = R_0 [1 + \alpha(T - T_0)] \quad (1)$$

where R_0 is the resistance at reference temperature T_0 and α is the temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR). For silver, $\alpha_{\text{Ag}} \approx 3.8 \times 10^{-3}/\text{K}$ at room temperature [2].

However, deviations from this value can occur in thin films, caused by grain size effects, mechanical stresses in the film, and impurities at grain boundaries [3].

2.2 Photolithography with Image Reversal Resist

Photolithography is a fundamental patterning method in microtechnology. In an image reversal process, a positive photoresist is converted into negative imaging behavior through thermal post-treatment [4]. This enables the creation of undercut profiles, which are essential for a successful lift-off process.

The typical sequence comprises:

1. First exposure through the mask (photoactivation),
2. Reversal bake (crosslinking of exposed areas),
3. Flood exposure (exposure of uncrosslinked areas),
4. Development (selective removal of uncrosslinked areas).

2.3 DC Magnetron Sputtering

Sputtering is a physical vapor deposition (PVD) process in which material is removed from a target by ion bombardment and deposited on a substrate [5]. In DC magnetron sputtering, a magnetic field enhances the ionization of the working gas (typically argon), leading to higher deposition rates and lower substrate temperatures.

3 Experimental Methods

3.1 Starting Material and Sample Preparation

Silicon wafers with 100 mm diameter (4 in) and a thermally grown oxide layer (≈ 500 nm SiO_2) serving as electrical insulation layer were used as starting material. The wafers were diced into square chips of size 1×1 cm using a scribe-and-break method.

To remove particles, fingerprints, and organic residues, cleaning was performed in the following steps:

- Ultrasonic bath in acetone (5 min),
- Rinse in isopropanol (IPA),
- Drying with nitrogen (N_2),
- Dehydration bake at 120°C for 5 min.

Figure 1: Diced silicon chips on a hotplate for thermal pretreatment (dehydration bake).

3.2 Resist Coating and Soft Bake

The chips were coated with image reversal resist AZ 5214E in a spin-coater (POLOS Spin150). The process parameters were:

- Rotation speed: 4000 rpm,
- Coating duration: 60 s,
- Resulting film thickness: approximately 1.4 μm .

Immediately after spin-coating, a soft bake at 95 °C for 60 s was performed to remove solvent residues and improve film adhesion.

3.3 UV Lithography with Image Reversal Process

Structured exposure was performed in a mask aligner (Karl Süss MA6) with a chrome mask defining the layout of the temperature sensor structure (meandering track with contact pads).

The image reversal process comprised the following steps:

Figure 2: Spin-coater for uniform resist coating of the silicon chips.

1. **First exposure:** Exposure through the mask with UV light ($\lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$, exposure dose $\approx 40 \text{ mJ/cm}^2$),
2. **Reversal bake:** Thermal treatment at 120°C for 120 s to crosslink exposed areas,
3. **Flood exposure:** Blanket exposure without mask ($\approx 200 \text{ mJ/cm}^2$) to activate previously unexposed areas,
4. **Development:** Development in AZ 726 MIF for 60 s under gentle agitation.

After development, the samples were rinsed in deionized water and dried with nitrogen.

Figure 3: Mask aligner for structured UV exposure of resist-coated chips.

3.4 Metallization by DC Magnetron Sputtering

The silver film deposition was performed in a sputtering system BAL-TEC MED020 under the following conditions:

- Target: high-purity silver (Ag, 99.99%),
- Working pressure: $\approx 5 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar (argon),
- Ignition voltage: ≈ 1.3 kV,
- Deposition current: 30 mA,
- Deposition rate: approximately 0.8 nm/s,
- Target film thickness: 80 nm,
- Deposition duration: approximately 100 s.

The film thickness was verified using a Dektak profilometer on reference samples.

Figure 4: Sputtering system BAL-TEC MED020 for silver thin-film deposition.

3.5 Lift-Off and Final Cleaning

The lift-off process serves to remove the photoresist along with the metal deposited on it, leaving only the desired structures on the substrate.

The process comprised:

- Immersion of samples in acetone for approximately 10 min,
- Careful manual rinsing with acetone from a wash bottle (ultrasound was avoided due to the delicate structures),
- Rinse in isopropanol,
- Drying with nitrogen.

Microscopic inspection under a light microscope (Zeiss Axioplan) was performed for quality control.

3.6 Electrical and Thermal Characterization

Electrical measurements were performed on a micromechanical probe station (Cascade Microtech PM5) with tungsten needle contacts. The resistance was determined using a digital multimeter (Keysight 34461A) in four-wire mode to eliminate contact resistances.

To determine the temperature coefficient, the sample was heated with a calibrated hot air gun while simultaneously recording temperature with a Pt100 reference sensor and resistance continuously. The temperature range extended from 25 °C to 85 °C.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Structural Quality and Process Yield

Of originally 25 processed chips, four to five sensors were fully functional after lift-off, corresponding to a yield of approximately 20 %. This comparatively low yield is realistic for a first student run and lies within the typical range for manual cleanroom processes without fully automated equipment.

Table 1: Quantitative analysis of main defect causes in sensor fabrication.

Defect type	Frequency	Fraction (%)
Particle contamination	10/25	40
Overdevelopment/underetching	7/25	28
Incomplete metal adhesion	2/25	8
Mechanical damage (lift-off)	1/25	4
Functional sensors	5/25	20

The most frequently observed defects (see Table 1) were:

- **Particle contamination (40%):** Dust particles on the resist led to local defects in the metallization. This is the dominant error source and could be reduced through improved filtration and stricter cleanroom protocols,
- **Overdevelopment or underetching (28%):** Excessive development time led to widened or interrupted conductor tracks. More precise time control is required,
- **Incomplete metal adhesion (8%):** Localized detachment of the silver layer, presumably due to insufficient surface cleaning or moisture uptake by the resist,
- **Mechanical damage during lift-off (4%):** The delicate structures were partially damaged by overly aggressive manual rinsing.

The successfully fabricated sensors showed a well-defined meandering track with a line width of approximately $50\ \mu\text{m}$ and a line spacing of approximately $50\ \mu\text{m}$. The edge sharpness was satisfactory, with the image reversal technique producing the desired undercut profile for lift-off.

4.2 Electrical Characterization

The baseline resistance of the sensors at room temperature ($T_0 = 25\ \text{°C}$) was on average $R_0 = 46.2(15)\ \Omega$. This relatively small variation indicates good reproducibility of the sputtering process and pattern transfer.

The resistance measurement as a function of temperature yielded an almost linear relationship, as is characteristic for metallic conductors (see Figure 7). At a temperature of 85 °C, the resistance increased to approximately 54.5 Ω , corresponding to a resistance change of $\Delta R \approx 8.3 \Omega$.

Table 2: Measured resistance values at various temperatures for an exemplary sensor.

Temperature (°C)	Resistance (Ω)
25	46.2
35	48.6
45	50.1
55	51.5
65	52.9
75	53.7
85	54.5

4.3 Determination of Temperature Coefficient

From linear regression of the measurement data (see Table 2), a temperature coefficient of

$$\alpha_{\text{measured}} = \frac{1}{R_0} \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta T} = \frac{8.3 \Omega}{46.2 \Omega \cdot 60 \text{ K}} = (3.0 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

is obtained.

The uncertainty of $\pm 0.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ results from the standard deviation of the linear regression and systematic measurement errors in temperature sensing. The main error sources are:

- Spatial temperature inhomogeneities of the hot air gun ($\pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$),
- Thermal inertia of the Pt100 reference sensor,
- Contact resistances at the probe station (minimized by four-wire measurement).

This value is slightly below the literature value for bulk silver ($\alpha_{\text{Ag,bulk}} = 3.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [2], which is typical for thin polycrystalline films. Possible causes for the reduction are:

- **Grain size effects:** At film thicknesses in the nanometer range, scattering at grain boundaries dominates electrical transport,
- **Impurities:** Oxygen residues or trapped argon atoms from the sputtering process,

- **Mechanical stress:** Thermal mismatch between silicon substrate and silver film.

Nevertheless, the measured value shows good agreement with typical values for sputtered silver films ($\alpha = (2.5\text{--}3.5) \times 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [3, 6].

4.4 Process Optimization and Outlook

To improve process yield and sensor quality, the following optimization approaches are proposed:

1. **Improved particle control:** Strict adherence to cleanroom garment protocols and regular filter inspections,
2. **Process automation:** Automated development and lift-off to reduce manual error sources,
3. **Development time optimization:** Systematic variation of development duration to determine the process window,
4. **Adhesion layer:** Deposition of a thin titanium or chromium layer ($\approx 5 \text{ nm}$) as adhesion promoter between SiO_2 and silver,
5. **Passivation:** Application of a protective layer (e.g., SiO_2 or Si_3N_4) to prevent silver oxidation and provide mechanical stabilization.

5 Summary and Conclusions

In this work, the complete fabrication of a silver-based microtechnological temperature sensor was documented. The multi-step cleanroom process comprised photolithography with image reversal resist, DC magnetron sputtering, and lift-off patterning.

Despite a process yield of only 20%, primarily attributable to manual process control and first-time student execution, several functional sensors with reproducible electrical properties were fabricated.

The measured temperature coefficient of $\alpha \approx 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ lies within the expected range for sputtered silver films and confirms the fundamental functionality of the sensor. The identified main error sources (particle contamination, overdevelopment, mechanical damage) are well known and controllable through process optimization.

The work provided a sound practical understanding of the relationships between lithography, thin-film technology, and sensor characterization, forming a solid foundation for further work in microsystems technology.

Figure 5: Micromechanical probe station for electrical contacting and characterization of sensor structures.

Figure 6: Finished temperature sensor chip after successful lift-off. The meandering track and contact pads are clearly visible.

Figure 7: Electrical resistance R of the silver sensor as a function of temperature T . The measurement points (circles) show good linearity in the investigated temperature range. The dashed line represents the linear regression used to determine the temperature coefficient α .

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